

Data management plan for "Freeze-Dried Chitosan Extract from Agaricus bisporus for Burn and Wound Care: A Hypoallergenic Solution for Skin Regeneration (FCEA-BW)" project

Version 1

Description

The proposed project aims to develop a prototype for an innovative combination of freeze-drying and extraction technologies, utilizing water for more efficient processing of mushroom biomass waste. This project focuses on creating a versatile range of high-value raw materials and bioproducts, aligning with the bio-economic goals of mushroom cultivation and the regional market demands. Additionally, the project will generate new knowledge and enhance the research, scientific, and engineering skills of students and industry professionals.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Freeze-Dried Chitosan Extract from Agaricus bisporus for Burn and Wound Care: A Hypoallergenic Solution for Skin Regeneration (FCEA-BW)

Researchers

Janis Baronins (0000-0002-0831-2733), Uldis Berzins (0000-0002-0585-1571), Aija Rautmane (0000-0002-2293-0837), Zemcenkovs Vjaceslavs (0000-0002-4097-9474), Andrei Shishkin (0000-0003-1944-5766), Maryna Zhylina (0000-0001-9074-6890), Pavels Gavrilovs (0000-0001-8727-2540), Inese Mierina (orcid:0000-0001-5573-9396), Ilmars Viksne (0000-0002-5560-5985), Hermanis Sorokins (0000-0001-5713-3291)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan for "Freeze-Dried Chitosan Extract from *Agaricus bisporus* for Burn and Wound Care: A Hypoallergenic Solution for Skin Regeneration (FCEA-BW)" project

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Freeze-Dried Chitosan Extract from *Agaricus bisporus* for Burn and Wound Care: A Hypoallergenic Solution for Skin Regeneration (FCEA-BW)

Project:

Data Management Plan | Data management plan for "Freeze-Dried Chitosan Extract from *Agaricus bisporus* for Burn and Wound Care: A Hypoallergenic Solution for Skin Regeneration (FCEA-BW)" project LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 12/12/2024

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Research data

Characterization of the extracts and description of the lyophilisation process parameters influence on the composition of the extract.

To produce chemically well controlled conditions sublimation in a flask (M1-M4).

To characterise and compare extracts made by following approaches (M2-M12):

- Homogenized pure mushroom and sublimated in a flask.
- Homogenized impure mushroom and sublimated in a flask.
- Homogenized pure mushroom - Freeze dried
- Homogenized impure mushroom - Freeze dried
- Freeze dried pure mushroom – homogenized.
- Freeze dried impure mushroom – homogenized.
- Freeze dried pure mushroom – homogenized – freeze dried.
- Freeze dried impure mushroom – homogenized – freeze dried.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection in this project is to advance the extraction and lyophilization technologies for developing chitosan extracts from *Agaricus bisporus*. The data will support the development of a scalable, efficient, and sustainable process, ultimately validating a prototype extraction unit (TRL4). Data will include experimental parameters, results from analytical techniques, and prototype testing outcomes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, the data collected in this project will be newly generated, specifically tailored for the development of the innovative chitosan extraction and lyophilization processes.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will benefit:

Researchers in the fields of green chemistry, biomedical engineering, and food science.

Industry stakeholders interested in sustainable extraction technologies.

Policy makers focusing on bioeconomy and sustainable practices.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Yes, search keywords will be included to optimize the reusability of the data.

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Yes, an embargo period is planned until the publication of related research articles. This will ensure proper academic acknowledgment.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Data will be deposited in Zenodo, a trusted open-access repository.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible through standard software tools like Microsoft Excel, Word, and Adobe Reader for PDFs.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Yes, all data formats (e.g., CSV, XLS, PDF) are widely recognized open formats that can be used with multiple software applications. These formats allow seamless integration and recombination with other data sets for further analysis.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Yes, the project will employ standard vocabularies and ontologies such as Dublin Core for metadata and relevant scientific taxonomies for experimental data. This ensures interoperability and consistent interpretation across systems.

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

The project emphasizes compliance with FAIR principles to maximize data compatibility and usability across various domains. Detailed documentation will accompany the data to facilitate understanding and integration by third parties.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC0 1.0

The project ensures that data is well-documented, openly accessible (where applicable), and compliant with standards for interoperability. Metadata, clear versioning, and keywords will make the data findable and reusable by researchers, industries, and educators. Embargo periods will be clearly defined, and access methods will be streamlined to encourage broad re-use.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-29

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Yes. Data quality assurance will be ensured through:

Regular Validation: Experimental data will be validated using established scientific methods and cross-checked against controls.

Standardized Procedures: Data collection and processing will follow standardized protocols to minimize errors.

Review and Audits: Periodic reviews and audits by project team members will verify data integrity and consistency.

Use of Reliable Tools: Analytical tools and software with proven accuracy will be employed to process and analyze the data.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs for making data FAIR during the project will be covered through:

Project Budget Allocation: A dedicated portion of the project budget will be allocated for data management activities, including FAIR compliance.

External Funding: Costs related to repository fees (e.g., Zenodo), data curation, and management tools will be included in the funding application.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Janis Baronins (0000-0002-0831-2733)

The project leader will oversee data management responsibilities, supported by a dedicated data manager. Specific tasks include:

Data Collection: Assigned to researchers conducting experiments.

Data Processing and Analysis: Handled by researchers with support from the data manager.

Metadata Creation and Documentation: Led by the data manager, ensuring adherence to standards.

Data Storage and Security: IT support staff will manage secure data storage and backup solutions.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Institutional Support: Hosting and maintaining data repositories through institutional infrastructure.

Open Access Funding: Costs associated with long-term data preservation and accessibility will be covered through institutional open access initiatives or by seeking external grants.

Collaborative Agreements: Partner organizations may contribute to sustaining FAIR data practices.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Security Measures Include:

Data Encryption: All sensitive and experimental data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest.

Access Control: Role-based access controls (RBAC) will limit access to authorized personnel only.

Regular Backups: Automated, encrypted backups will be maintained in geographically redundant locations.

Firewall and Antivirus Systems: Institutional IT systems will ensure network security and protection against potential cyber threats.

Application of Security Measures:

Encrypted storage will be applied on institutional servers.

Researchers will use secure data transfer protocols (e.g., SFTP) when sharing data.

Periodic audits will ensure compliance with security policies.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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